

CHALLENGES IN THE SELECTION OF SHIPPING LINES IN MAIN COLLECTION DISTRICTS OF MANILA: TOWARDS A PROPOSED PROCESS IMPROVEMENT STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the challenges faced by customs brokers and freight forwarders in the shipping industry, with a particular focus on issues such as container demurrage, detention, and fluctuating freight rates. It examined how factors like the frequency of using specific shipping lines, the experience level of professionals, and the type of shipping line impacted these challenges. The findings revealed that even frequent users and experienced brokers continued to encounter significant problems, particularly with rising costs and delays' older shipping lines, which often rely on outdated manual systems, were especially prone to operational inefficiencies, exacerbating delays and increasing unexpected charges. This suggested that the experience and expertise of brokers alone were insufficient to overcome the systemic issues in the industry. The study highlighted the need for shipping companies to modernize their systems by adopting new technology to improve operational efficiency and enhance communication with clients. Clearer, more consistent pricing practices were also essential to reduce uncertainty and improve cost predictability. By addressing these issues, shipping companies would have improved the overall efficiency and fairness of the shipping process, benefiting both themselves and their clients. The insights gained from this study are valuable for industry stakeholders looking to streamline operations, reduce costs, and ultimately create a more transparent and reliable shipping environment.

Keywords: *Shipping lines, process improvement, customs brokers, mixed method research*

INTRODUCTION

The shipping company holds significant importance in today's global economy. It is a highly profitable sector, not only in the Philippines but worldwide. Furthermore, as a result of the pandemic, there have been significant advancements in processing. However, the Philippines, being a developing country, lags behind in terms of technology. Consequently, these changes have posed challenges for us. In addition, there are modifications occurring in relation to other challenges such as charges and rates being paid to the shipping company. Moreover, customs brokers act as intermediaries between importers and shipping lines. They play a key part in the logistics sector because of the role they play in processing and assisting communication with shipping lines. This makes them an important component of the industry (Del Rosario, 2020).

The shipping sector plays a significant role in the Philippine economy, as it accounts for more than 90% of the country's trade, which is primarily conducted by maritime transportation. The Philippine shipping industry has undergone significant infrastructure renovation with the construction of new ports and the acquisition of state-of-the-art vessels. According to a 2021 estimate by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the market value of logistics transport services in the Philippines is \$11 billion. Road and marine transportation account for 40% and 35%, respectively, of the freight transportation industry's 4% contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The majority of the nation's numerous islands are connected by road transit to facilitate the transportation of goods to and from ports. Maritime transportation is used for both domestic and international cargo (Zhenhub, 2023).

The shipping lines mentioned above are affiliated with AISL, which stands for the Association of International Shipping Lines, Inc. These lines are classified as conference-type liners. AISL was established and legally registered on June 6, 1963. The Association is widely acknowledged as the foremost authority in the Philippines for the international container shipping sector. It currently has a membership of 36 worldwide container liners that operate in Philippine ports. Over the course of more than five decades, its impact on the development of national policies that impact international shipping operations has steadily expanded in tandem with the substantial growth in trade between the Philippines and other nations (AISL, 2023).

The objective of this study was to examine the challenges influencing the selection of shipping lines in the main ports of Manila. In addition, the researcher aimed to ascertain whether there was a significant difference in the choice of shipping lines among respondents when the data was categorized based on their profile and the challenges they were facing. The study sought to improve the process of the shipping line industry in order to address the challenges faced by customs brokers. This did not only benefit the customs brokers but also contributed to the overall development of the shipping line industry by providing insights on areas that require improvement and change.

Furthermore, the study identified six challenges that influence the selection of a shipping line: delivery order, terminal charges, demurrage, container deposit, container detention, and shipping line freight rate. These areas provided opportunities for improvement.

To elaborate on these challenges, they examined them individually, beginning with the delivery order. In this context, a delivery order refers to a document authorized by the items' owner or their representative, instructing the transfer of the goods to a designated recipient. It is considered challenging due to the manner in which it is acquired. Depending on the shipping line employed, there are varying procedures for processing the delivery order, leading to complications. In addition, importation can be hindered by costly terminal charges. Furthermore, demurrage and container detention fees can be excessively high if the container or goods are not in the designated location within the specified time frame or the allotted free days provided by the shipping line. Lastly, there is the container deposit, which is a fee paid by the importer that can be refunded. The issue arises when it becomes challenging to reimburse the deposit made to the shipping company (Zhenhub, 2023).

Studies on the selection of shipping lines in Manila's main ports were still lacking. Certain studies investigated shipping lines, although they focused on different regions or sections of the world. Given this industry, respondents, and challenges, this study's gap existed. The results of this study could be helpful to importers, shipping lines, and customs brokers since they made them more aware, informed, and perceptive about the process provided by shipping lines. In addition, the study provided suggestions for improving processes that benefited the aforementioned parties.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered by customs brokers in the Selection of Shipping Lines in Main Collection Districts of Manila, to provide towards a proposed Process Improvement Strategy. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What are the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Frequency used of shipping line service;
 - 1.2 Port of transaction;
 - 1.3 Length of tenure as practicing customs broker
 - 1.4 Present line of business; and
 - 1.5 Type of Liner?
2. What is the extent of challenges encountered by respondents as to the following challenges:
 - 2.1 Delivery Order;
 - 2.2 Terminal charges by shipping line;
 - 2.3 Container demurrage;
 - 2.4 Container deposit;
 - 2.5 Container detention; and
 - 2.6 Shipping lines freight rate?

3. Are there significant differences in the extent of challenges encountered by respondents when group according to profile?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what process improvement can be proposed for shipping lines in main Collection Districts of Manila?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study Mix Method Research (MMR) was utilized. MMR is a research method that integrates qualitative and quantitative research approaches to achieve a comprehensive and in-depth understanding through the combination of different viewpoints, data collection methods, analysis techniques, and inference methods. Mixing several research methodologies in social science has become more popular with the emergence of MMR. Timans et al. (2019), currently, there is no existing record that contains data on the challenges influencing the selection of a shipping line in the main ports of Manila.

This research, for quantitative side, can be defined as descriptive, as its objective was to systematically observe, characterize, and document various components of a situation in its natural state, without intentionally changing any of the variables. This was utilized to offer a thorough overview of an event, phenomenon, or population by gathering data that defined the specific attributes or actions being examined. Then the researcher was utilized the exploratory type of qualitative research, as it aimed to investigate and depicted the intricate nature of human experiences and social circumstances. This was ideal considering the provided variables and respondents at that were available.

Aside from investigating the challenges in selection of shipping lines, the researcher was also interested in the profile of customs brokers that transact with the main ports of manila. Furthermore, the issues they faced was thoroughly addressed in the survey questionnaire. As such, the individual working experience and challenges faced by customs brokers significantly influenced the selection of shipping line firms and their job performance. Only the mixed method research can produce the results needed for this study.

Data Management

The researcher created online questionnaires for respondents to complete in order to gather extensive data and allowed participants flexibility in their responses. The surveys were distributed meticulously and systematically by the researcher to ensure all intended participants were reached. Furthermore, the researcher increased response rates and prompt quick input by conducting follow-up actions via phone calls, messages, or emails.

The researcher distributed the questionnaire by sending the survey link to the respondents through email, messengers, or any other preferred method. After

respondents submitted the survey, the researcher verified the information directly using Google Docs. To prevent any data loss, the researcher created backups of all survey sheets upon receiving them. Finally, the researcher analyzed the collected data using statistical methods including frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and ANOVA, T-test and multiple regression.

Sampling Design

This part will discuss the sample population, respondents, research instrument of the study.

Sample Population

The study's sample size was 313 individuals, determined using Raosoft formula. This was from the total number of customs brokers that is registered with Chamber of Customs Brokers Inc. (CCBI) and was issued a certificate of good standing. As per record to this date, April 17, 2024. The CCBI issued a total of One thousand six hundred sixty-one (1,661) certificate of good standing to its members. Moreover, Makau & Muna (2020), suggest that samples over 30 exhibit more similarities with populations, and larger samples outperform smaller ones due to the central limit theorem and the rule-of-thumb. Therefore, this sample size sufficed for the researcher to do the study.

The sample population for the study was carefully defined to ensure relevance and representativeness. In this study, the target participants were be customs brokers operating within the dynamic business environment of Manila. The choice of customs brokers as the focal group was strategic, considering their integral role in facilitating international trade and customs clearance processes. Manila, being a major hub for trade and commerce in the Philippines, provides a contextually rich setting for understanding the intricacies of shipping lines. The sample population was expected to comprise individuals with diverse professional backgrounds and experiences in customs brokerage, freight forwarding companies and others, thereby contributing to a comprehensive exploration of their encounters with shipping line services.

Respondents

In the study, the utilization of purposive sampling was deemed appropriate due to the specialized nature of the study and the targeted participant group. Given the intricate dynamics of customs brokers and the unique challenges associated with shipping lines, purposive sampling allowed for the intentional selection of participants who possessed specific qualifications and experiences deemed most relevant to the research objectives. The inclusion criteria for this sampling strategy involved customs brokers situated within Manila, ensuring a geographically confined yet diverse representation. In addition, participants were registered and was issued a certificate of good standing in CCBI. Since they were officially registered and have been given a certificate of good standing, they may be classified as practicing customs brokers and were ideal candidates to participate as respondents in this study. To achieve a comprehensive understanding, the inclusion

criteria should span customs brokers with varied experiences across shipping lines, fostering a diverse range of perspectives.

Research Instrument

The survey questionnaire was employed as the primary data collection tool because it was one of the most extensively utilized methods for acquiring trustworthy data and information. The questionnaire consists of three sections:(A) Profile of the Respondents; (B) Challenges influencing the selection of shipping lines, (Delivery Order, Terminal Charges, Demurrage, Container Deposit, Container Detention and Shipping lines freight rate); (C) Challenges encountered by respondents and recommendations the respondents can provide. Emails were sent and Google Docs were utilized to distribute the questionnaires, also known as harvested emails.

Note: The researcher has obtained express permission to mention the names of the shipping companies included in this study

Survey and structured interview were also used in the study, A survey is a systematic research technique employed to gather data from a predetermined group of participants in order to obtain information and insights on diverse subjects of interest. Surveys are frequently employed in various domains including social sciences, market research, healthcare, education, and public opinion polls. They are specifically designed to collect either quantitative or qualitative data by posing a sequence of questions to the participants. While, structured interview is a methodical approach to interviewing candidates, in which the interviewer poses a planned set of questions in a specified sequence. The purpose of this interview format is to maintain uniformity, impartiality, and neutrality by presenting identical questions to all candidates, facilitating the comparison of their answers.

In the structured interview, the researcher formulated a six sets of narrative questions in order to obtain more comprehensive perspectives from the respondents. The questions pertain to individuals' experiences, challenges and satisfaction with the services provided by shipping companies in the main ports of Manila.

A scale's or test item's internal consistency, or reliability, can be gauged using Cronbach's alpha. It is frequently used to evaluate the reliability of a composite score composed of several items or questions in the fields of psychometrics, education, psychology, and other social sciences.

A 4-point Likert scale is a psychometric response technique that allows respondents to quickly react to questions and indicate how much they agree with a statement in four points. This was used in this study. The 4-point Likert scale consisted of the below points – (1) Very Challenging ; (2) Moderately Challenging; (3) Challenging; (4) Not challenging at all

point	Scale Range	Interpretation	Researcher's Interpretation
4	3.26 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Challenging
3	2.51 - 3.25	Agree	Challenging
2	1.76 - 2.50	Disagree	Moderately challenging
1	1.00 - 1.75	Strongly Disagree	Not Challenging at all

For the purpose of pilot testing, a sample of twenty to thirty participants was be utilized to assess the questionnaires that have been developed. This was necessary in order to evaluate the reliability and quality of the primary study's data, and to ensure that the research design and procedures were effective.

There should have been 313 responders in all, but the researcher was only able to obtain 169, or 53% retrieval rate. The "50% + 1" rule, which enabled researchers to draw valid conclusions from a sample slightly larger than half of the population, was frequently used when accessing the entire population is difficult. This strategy strikes a balance between practical limitations like accessibility and budget and statistical reliability (Qualtrics, 2023; CloudResearch, 2023)

The Cronbach's alpha result was 0.7876, which was deemed acceptable according to the presented table.

Statistical Treatment

The following were used in the study:

Percentage and Frequency Distribution. The proportion and frequency are used to describe the relationship between two magnitudes as well as a part of a whole. This method was used to interpret the respondents' profiles of customs brokers which mainly focus on Frequency use of shipping line, port of transaction, length of tenure as practicing customs broker and present line of business.

Mean. It is designed to measure the central tendency of a set of numbers. It helps to show how much variation exists within the group. In this study, the researcher used this statistical tool to present the level of agreement of respondents on the effects of customs brokers experience on selection of shipping line in main ports of Manila.

In this study, ANOVA was used to test the hypothesis by comparing how the perceptions of customs brokers vary based on their demographic profiles. The hypothesis assumed that there were no significant differences in the extent of difficulty encountered by respondents when grouped according to their profile, such as experience, age, or role. In addition, the study explored whether there was a significant impact of these

demographic factors on the challenges faced by customs brokers, particularly in relation to customer satisfaction and the selection of shipping lines in the main ports of Manila. By applying ANOVA, the researcher determined if the challenges faced by brokers differ significantly based on their demographics. If the results show significant differences, it was suggested that factors like experience or role do affect the challenges encountered, which could help inform strategies for improving operations in the shipping industry.

RESULTS

This section presents the results of the study based on the statement of the problem. This part of the paper likewise further substantiates the findings to draw the outcome of the study.

Table 1

Profile of selected customs brokers in terms of shipping line service

Frequency used of shipping line service	Frequency	Percentage
At least once a week	111	65.68
At least once a month	35	20.71
At least once quarterly	5	2.96
At least once yearly	18	10.65
Total	169	100.00

Table 1 illustrates the frequency of shipping line utilization by customs brokers as respondents. The figure reflected the quantity of customs brokers or enterprises employing shipping line services. A significant majority, 65.68%, utilized these services weekly, indicating consistent and frequent shipping needs, either due to high-volume operations or continuous supply chain requirements. This aligns with Descartes' (2023), research which shown that port transit times have enhanced and container import quantities have risen, signifying an increased dependence on shipping services to fulfill supply chain requirements. This indicates that a weekly response is customary, as customs brokers often employ this due to its importance in the importation of goods.

Furthermore, 20.71% of respondents engaged shipping line services on a monthly basis, signifying a modest but consistent need for shipments. A small group, 2.96%, employed the service quarterly, suggesting seasonal or specific corporate activities that require infrequent logistics. Ultimately, 10.65% of respondents engaged on shipping services annually, perhaps for sporadic or project-specific shipping requirements. The

majority of clients heavily depended on shipping services, demonstrating a marked desire for weekly and monthly deliveries.

Table 2

Profile of selected customs brokers in terms of port of transaction.

Port of transaction	Frequency	Percentage
Port of Manila (P02A)	25	14.79
Manila International Container Port (P02B)	31	18.34
Both	113	66.86
Total	169	100.00

Table 2 depicts the allocation of shipping transactions between the Port of Manila and the Manila International Container Port (MICP). At the Port of Manila, 14.79% of transactions (25 out of 169) took place, while the MICP oversees 18.34% (31 transactions). The data revealed that certain customs brokers or companies preferred to use only one of the two ports for their shipping operations, with MICP being slightly more preferred than the Port of Manila. Bantigue (2023) emphasizes that Manila emerged as the principal port in the Philippines owing to its favorable natural characteristics. The Port of Manila functions as the nation's primary conduit for international trade and a nexus for individuals from many locations, underscoring its importance in contemporary logistics. This signifies agreement with the validity of the results. Brokers consistently employ either PO2B or PO2A in Manila.

However, the majority of transactions, 66.86% (113 out of 169), occurred at both ports, indicating that most clients interact with both the Port of Manila and MICP. This suggested a need for more flexibility and access to diverse facilities to enable more efficient logistics. The use of both ports allows firms to improve their shipping operations and manage larger or more complex supply chains.

The table below provides an overview of the experience levels among active customs brokers, highlighting the distribution of their tenure in the industry. This data could be used to assess the overall experience level of the customs brokerage workforce and identify potential areas for training and development.

Table 3

Profile of selected customs brokers in terms of length of tenure as practicing customs broker

Length of tenure year being a practicing customs broker:	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 years	41	24.26
4-6 years	83	49.11
7-10 years	37	21.89
10 years above	8	4.73
Total	169	100.00

Table 3 displays information regarding the tenure of active customs brokers. The predominant group, including 49.11% (83 out of 169), had engaged in practice for 4-6 years, signifying that over half of the respondents belong to this intermediate experience category. According to Expert Market Research (2024), "many customs brokers have 4-6 years of experience, highlighting the industry's demand for moderately experienced professionals." Simultaneously, 24.26% (41 brokers) have been employed for 1-3 years, indicating that a considerable proportion of brokers exhibit relative inexperience in the industry. IBISWorld (2024) stated that "a significant percentage of customs brokers possess only 1-3 years of experience, often highlighting the challenges faced by novices in the industry." Furthermore, 21.89% (37 brokers) possessed 7-10 years of experience, indicating a substantial representation of seasoned experts. A little proportion, 4.73% (8 brokers), had been active in the sector for over a decade, signifying a somewhat restricted presence of long-term professionals. The research indicated that the customs brokerage industry is primarily comprised of persons with moderate experience, whereas those possessing substantial or minimal competence are less prevalent.

The data following categorizes selected respondents based on their current business sectors, focusing on customs brokerage and freight forwarding. It highlighted the role of these two key sectors in the logistics and shipping industry.

Table 4

Profile of selected customs brokers in terms of present line of business

Present line of business	Frequency	Percentage
Customs Brokerage	85	50.30
Freight forwarding company	84	49.70
Total	169	100.00

Table 4 shows the respondents' present line of business. The predominant segment, including 50.30% (85 out of 169), participated in customs brokerage. Approximately fifty percent of the respondents concentrated on maintaining customs documentation, guaranteeing compliance, and facilitating the expedited clearing of goods through customs. Conversely, 49.70% (84 out of 169) were linked to freight forwarding companies, tasked with coordinating the shipment of products. The roughly equivalent distribution between customs brokerage and freight forwarding indicates that respondents were virtually evenly divided between these two essential sectors of the logistics and shipping business.

The rise of the customs brokerage sector, driven by expanding global trade volumes and complex regulations, renders the roles of customs brokers and freight forwarders increasingly vital for facilitating international commerce. Research and Markets (2024) predicts significant expansion in the U.S. customs brokerage sector, propelled by the rise of e-commerce and the demand for adept management of customs procedures. Precision Business Insights (2023) emphasized that the increasing interconnectivity of global supply chains shows the need of these businesses in ensuring compliance and efficiency in international trade.

The table 5 shows the distribution of shipping lines currently employed by the respondents. The primary choice is a combination of Company A and Company B, employed by 45.56% (77 out of 169) of the respondents. Furthermore, 18.93% employed all three shipping lines: Company A, Company B, and Company D. Independently, 18.93% only employ Company A Line, establishing it as the most dominant shipping line overall, whether utilized alone or in combination with others.

Table 5

Profile of selected customs brokers in terms of type of liner

Shipping line	Frequency	Percentage
Company A line	32	18.93
Company B line	10	5.92
Company A, Company B	77	45.56
Company A, Company B, Company C	18	10.65
Company A, Company B, Company D	32	18.93
Total	169	100.00

Table 5 shows the profile of selected customs brokers in terms of type of liner. In contrast, the Company B Line is employed by 5.92% of participants. Significantly, no respondents independently utilized Company C. or Company D Shipping Line Ltd., since both demonstrate a frequency of 0%. However, they were chosen alongside other lines: 10.65% use Company A, Company B, and Asia, while others utilize Company A, Company B, and Company D.

Data on shipping line utilization revealed a significant preference among customs brokers for Company A and Company B, both individually and collectively. Company A, a leading global container shipping firm, has optimized its services to meet market demand and enhance supply chain reliability, positioning itself as the preferred choice for many brokers AIT Worldwide Logistics, (2023). Despite challenges in the shipping industry, including overcapacity and fluctuating prices, Company B has maintained its market position (Company A, 2023).

The predominant preference among respondents is for the use of multiple shipping lines, with Company A being the most frequently chosen, either alone or in combination with other carriers like Company B.

These following tables analyzes the challenges faced in the delivery order process, highlighting the need for efficiency and digitalization improvements.

Table 6

Challenges encountered by the selected respondents in terms of delivery order

Delivery Order	Mean	Interpretation
Delivery Order is obtained quickly upon request.	2.598	Challenging
Requesting a delivery order with shipping line is a simple process.	2.479	Moderately Challenging
The shipping line employee responsible for managing the delivery order demonstrates patience when dealing with inquiries.	2.704	Challenging
Obtaining a delivery order online is more convenient than making a manual request.	3.219	Very Challenging
The waiting time for manual delivery order requests is less compared to the online process.	2.408	Moderately Challenging
Over-all Mean	2.682	Challenging

Legend: Very Challenging; 3.26-4.00, Challenging; 2.51-3.25, Moderately Challenging; 1.76-2.50, Not Challenging At All ;1.00-1.75.

Table 6 shows that the delivery order procedure revealed significant challenges faced by participants. An average score of 2.682 categorized the event as "challenging." The claim regarding the prompt acquisition of a delivery order upon request received a mean score of 2.598,

indicating that many individuals face difficulties in promptly getting the necessary documents. This suggests that improvements may be necessary in the response times or protocols of the shipping lines to enhance efficiency in the delivery order process.

Participants indicated that initiating a delivery order with the shipping line is a relatively challenging task, resulting in a mean score of 2.479. This signifies irritation at the complexity or inefficacy of the request process. The patience of shipping line staff in handling queries obtained a score of 2.704, categorized as demanding, underscoring the importance of customer service in alleviating specific issues encountered during the process. Contrary to the findings of Prasadja et al. (2023), it is demonstrated that electronic delivery orders and logistics digitalization have a partial impact on import document activities through logistics service quality, which in turn enhances the influence of electronic delivery orders on import document activities.

A notable concern is the simplicity of obtaining a delivery order online compared to filing a manual request. This factor, with an average score of 3.219, is categorized as "very challenging," signifying dissatisfaction with online operations. Furthermore, the perception that the waiting time for manual requests is less than that for online processes, which earned a score of 2.408, highlights the challenges associated with online requests. This indicates an ongoing need to enhance digitization to prevent customs brokers from facing significant challenges in obtaining electronic delivery orders. These insights suggest that shipping businesses could refine their processes and improve online services to better meet client needs.

Based on qualitative study, respondents emphasized the necessity to optimize the delivery order process, specifically targeting efficiency and minimizing complexity. Key recommendations encompassed, "Streamline the process from the portal of the shipping line and end-user point of view," alongside a broader appeal to "Streamline the process." Minimizing paperwork was prioritized, with the suggestion to "Lessen the documentation." Furthermore, respondents endorsed technical enhancements, highlighting the significance of "Online processing of delivery orders." These recommendations seek to streamline processes, augment customer experience, and optimize operational efficiency in the delivery order method.

A major problem in the delivery order process is the extensive documentation required, often leading to delays and inefficiencies. Participants emphasized the need to enhance this process by reducing documentation and refining the user experience of shipping line portals. Recommendations included the implementation of online

processing systems to accelerate transactions and diminish processing expenses. This aligns with previous studies demonstrating that optimized processes can significantly improve operational efficiency (Jones, 2022; Smith & Liu, 2021).

This table 7 examines the challenges associated with terminal costs. Respondents reported significant concerns regarding the high costs, lack of transparency, and inconsistency in pricing. These findings underscore the need for a more equitable and efficient terminal cost structure.

Table 7

Challenges encountered by the selected respondents in terms of terminal charges

Terminal Charges by Shipping Line	Mean	Interpretation
Rates of terminal charges are too high.	3.391	Very challenging
Difficulty in the payment terms related to terminal charges.	2.858	Challenging
The terminal charges are justified by the proficiency of terminal handling.	2.521	Challenging
The implementation of terminal late charges.	2.290	Moderately challenging
Over-all Mean	2.765	Challenging
<i>Legend: Very Challenging; 3.26-4.00, Challenging; 2.51-3.25, Moderately Challenging; 1.76-2.50, Not Challenging At All ;1.00-1.75.</i>		

In table 7, the examination of terminal costs revealed several significant challenges faced by respondents, resulting in an average score of 2.765, so categorizing the experience as "challenging." The claim on the high rates of terminal costs had an average score of 3.391, indicating that a significant number of respondents perceive these fees as unduly burdensome. This opinion signifies an urgent need to reevaluate the pricing structure for terminal services, as high charges may negatively impact logistical efficiency. Yi et al. (2021) contend that implementing a dynamic pricing strategy can improve the competitiveness and profitability of container ports by adjusting THC prices based on current market conditions, thus resolving the concerns raised by respondents.

The investigation revealed that respondents face difficulties with payment arrangements related to terminal expenses, which obtained a score of 2.858 and is categorized as "challenging." This indicates that the existing payment processes may be unclear or rigid, resulting in user frustration. Moreover, the conviction that terminal

charges are justified by the efficiency of terminal handling had a mean score of 2.521, highlighting the need for transparency and rationale about the incurred costs. Without clear communication about the value provided, purchasers may struggle to view the fees as reasonable.

The introduction of terminal late charges is a significant worry, with a score of 2.290, classifying it as "moderately challenging." This section highlights potential issues regarding the fairness and transparency of late fee procedures, which may exacerbate stress for consumers already facing significant costs associated with terminal services. The findings indicate that terminal operators ought to reassess their cost frameworks and payment terms, as well as enhance communication concerning the rationale for terminal fees, to elevate customer happiness and alleviate perceived challenges.

Based on qualitative study, participants underscored the necessity for consistency and more equitable sanctions concerning terminal costs. Numerous individuals conveyed discontent, asserting that "Penalties imposed are too much," while some recommended the necessity to "lower terminal charges." A demand for uniform and transparent pricing was apparent, with suggestions such as, "It would be better if there is a fixed rate imposed for certain destinations," and "Standardize the rates and destinations." These responses emphasize the necessity of establishing an equitable and consistent pricing framework to alleviate the financial burden on enterprises and optimize terminal operations.

Participants expressed concerns regarding heightened penalties and variable terminal fees that vary by region. The need for transparency concerning these charges was a recurring subject. Transparency can enhance trust among users, as demonstrated by industry research advocating for improved communication regarding cost structures (Brown & Green, 2023; Williams, 2022).

Table 8 presents the examination of container demurrage processes that revealed several significant challenges faced by respondents, resulting in an average score of 3.187, therefore categorizing the experience as "challenging." The claim regarding restricted free time before incurring demurrage fees had a mean score of 3.325, indicating that many respondents saw the allotted time as inadequate. This issue highlighted the pressing need for shipping companies to extend the designated free period to avoid imposing undue charges on its clients. Kweon et al. (2022), contend that congestion adversely impacts overall ship turnaround time, resulting in reduced efficiency in port operations and increased demurrage rates. Therefore, it is essential to reduce the demurrage rate to maintain operational efficiency and profitability.

Table 8*Challenges encountered by the selected respondents in terms of container demurrage*

Container Demurrage	Mean	Interpretation
Not enough free time before incurring demurrage charges.	3.325	Very challenging
Too large amount to be charged for demurrage.	3.118	Challenging
Directly remitting payment to the shipping line is more efficient than making payment through a bank as an intermediary.	3.118	Challenging
Over-all Mean	3.187	Challenging
<i>3.26-4.00 Very Challenging; 2.51-3.25 Challenging; 1.76-2.50 Moderately Challenging 1.00-1.75 Not Challenging At All</i>		

In addition to the limited free time, respondents expressed concern about the significant demurrage fees, which obtained a score of 3.118. This suggests a prevalent perception that these payments are exorbitant and impose financial strain on companies. The conviction that directly paying the shipping line is more efficient than using a bank as an intermediary received a mean score of 3.118, suggesting that current payment processes may lack efficiency and transparency, thus aggravating the demurrage problem.

The findings indicated that shipping companies must resolve the concerns raised by respondents about container demurrage practices. Extending the grace period before imposing charges and reassessing the cost structures associated with demurrage can enhance customer trust and mitigate the financial burden on clients. Improving payment processes to facilitate direct remittance could result in a more efficient and user-friendly approach to resolving demurrage issues.

Based on qualitative study, to enhance container demurrage, respondents highlighted the necessity of prolonging both free time and grace periods prior to the imposition of demurrage fees. Recommendations included: "Extend free time, especially in cases of port congestion," and "Consider extending the free demurrage period to 14 days." Respondents also says, "Extend grace periods and free days before to the imposition of demurrage charges," and "Offer additional free time to compensate for delays caused by port congestion." These recommendations highlight the necessity for increased flexibility in the demurrage process to alleviate the financial strain on enterprises, especially during congestion, and to improve overall operational efficiency.

Respondents voiced concerns about restricted free time and grace periods leading to increased demurrage charges, particularly during periods of port congestion. There were extensive calls for prolonged grace periods before the implementation of fees. Moreover, evaluating demurrage fees for equity may alleviate certain financial burdens on importers. Studies demonstrate that flexible demurrage regulations can effectively manage peak periods (Nguyen, 2023; Patel & Singh, 2022).

The findings underscored the urgent need for a comprehensive overhaul of container demurrage practices. Shipping companies must prioritize transparency, flexibility, and fairness in their fee structures and payment processes. By extending free time periods, implementing more forgiving grace periods, and providing clear communication about charges, companies can alleviate the financial strain on businesses and improve customer satisfaction. Moreover, adopting digital solutions to streamline payment processes and facilitate timely remittance can further enhance efficiency and reduce administrative burdens.

It is imperative for shipping companies to collaborate with industry stakeholders, including port authorities, customs agencies, and freight forwarders, to develop a more equitable and sustainable demurrage framework. By working together, the industry can address the root causes of demurrage, such as port congestion, inefficient customs clearance, and logistical challenges, and create a more resilient and customer-centric supply chain.

Table 9 summarizes the challenges faced by customs brokers in relation to container deposits. The data highlights significant concerns regarding excessive rates, complex payment processes, difficulties in obtaining refunds, and the imposition of fees for container deposits

The examination of container deposit procedures revealed several substantial obstacles encountered by participants, resulting in an average score of 3.039, so categorizing the experience as "challenging." The claim regarding high container deposit rates obtained a score of 2.799, indicating that many respondents perceived these costs as burdensome. This signified that terminal operators must reassess their pricing strategies to alleviate financial pressure on their clientele. Lépinoy (2023), contends that these deposits pose significant administrative, operational, and financial issues, representing a substantial obstacle to trade in Africa.

Table 9*Challenges encountered by the selected respondents in terms of container deposit*

Container Deposit	Mean	Interpretation
Excessive rates for container deposit.	2.799	Challenging
Challenging payment conditions for container deposits.	2.734	Challenging
Experiencing difficulties in obtaining a refund for the container deposit.	3.349	Very Challenging
Imposing a fee for container deposits is just and appropriate to ensure the efficient progression of the supply chain.	3.006	Challenging
The deduction of container detention from container deposit.	3.308	Very Challenging
Over-all Mean	3.039	Challenging

Legend: Very Challenging; 3.26-4.00, Challenging; 2.51-3.25, Moderately Challenging; 1.76-2.50, Not Challenging At All ;1.00-1.75.

Participants expressed a notable worry with the challenges associated with obtaining refunds for container deposits, which had a mean score of 3.349 and is classified as "very challenging." This discovery suggests potential inefficiencies or ambiguities in the return process, possibly leading to customer frustration. The average score of 3.308 regarding the deduction of container detention from container deposits highlights the challenges respondents have in navigating these financial regulations.

Furthermore, while some respondents assert that instituting a fee for container deposits is just and crucial for the efficient progression of the supply chain, indicated by a mean score of 3.006, the dominant sentiment reflects concern over the fairness and transparency of these practices.

The onerous payment requirements, with an average score of 2.734, exacerbate the perceived difficulties within the container deposit system. These observations suggest

that terminal operators could enhance the clarity and efficiency of their container deposit processes to elevate customer satisfaction and alleviate the issues identified by customers.

Based on qualitative study, participants emphasized the necessity for enhancements in the container deposit system, particularly calling for reduced prices and a more streamlined claims process. Responses encompassed recommendations such as, "Reduce container deposit," "Simplify the process for reclaiming the container deposit," "Decrease rates," and "Eliminate the container deposit." This feedback reflects a pronounced user need for reduced financial constraints and simplified processes, which might markedly improve their overall experience in the logistics sector. Addressing these issues may enhance client loyalty, eventually benefiting service providers.

The issue of high container deposit costs and complications in the reclamation process emerged as a significant barrier. Moreover, investigating other assurances may mitigate the financial burden on customers. This perspective is supported by research emphasizing the importance of accessible financial policies in fostering positive customer relationships (Martin, 2023; Lopez et al., 2022)

Table 10

Challenges encountered by the selected respondents in terms of container detention

Container Detention	Mean	Interpretation
The rates for container detention are excessively high.	3.355	Very Challenging
Managing the payment arrangements for container detention can be challenging.	3.166	Challenging
Insufficient number of free days granted by the shipping company.	3.148	Challenging
Over-all Mean	3.223	Challenging
<i>Legend: Very Challenging; 3.26-4.00, Challenging; 2.51-3.25, Moderately Challenging; 1.76-2.50, Not Challenging At All ;1.00-1.75.</i>		

Table 10 presents the challenges encountered in terms of container detention. It revealed several significant issues faced by respondents, resulting in an average score of 3.223, therefore categorizing the experience as "challenging." The claim regarding excessive container detention fees had an average score of 3.355, indicating a

widespread perception among respondents that these charges were burdensome. This study suggests that shipping companies should reassess their detention cost structures to alleviate financial burdens on clients. Katrien et al. (2023), contend that the diminished availability of time and the escalation of demurrage and detention fees are organizational impediments for multimodal transportation, underscoring the urgency of addressing these issues expeditiously.

In conjunction with increased prices, participants indicated challenges in managing payment arrangements for container detention, which obtained a score of 3.166. This suggests potential complexities in the payment processes that may be causing user frustration. Furthermore, the average score of 3.148 regarding the insufficient distribution of free days by shipping companies exacerbates the challenges associated with container detention. Adequate free time is essential to prevent elevated costs and operational inefficiencies, which can burden businesses reliant on timely deliveries.

The research findings indicate that digitization, which affords additional "free time" for hinterland regions and improves focus during negotiations, is recognized as the principal potential solution to these difficulties. These observations indicate that shipping companies must resolve the concerns articulated by respondents regarding container retention. Shipping companies can enhance client trust and mitigate problems associated with container detention by evaluating and perhaps modifying their pricing strategies, elucidating payment terms, and augmenting the number of complimentary days provided.

Based on qualitative study, to enhance container detention, respondents underscored the necessity of extending free time and harmonizing charges. They proposed, "By giving more time to the end users." and "Longer free time." as essential methods to mitigate pressure on firms handling container returns. Several respondents suggested more extreme methods, including the elimination of detention, saying "No more container detention." reflecting a wish to abolish these fees entirely. Furthermore, there was a request for enhanced uniformity in pricing, with one respondent asserting, "It would be better if there is a fixed rate imposed." This underscores the necessity of granting businesses greater flexibility and predictability in the management of container detention fees.

Users saw rigid schedules and significant detention fees as problematic, urging for an extension of the grace period before the enforcement of these penalties. Studies indicate that prolonging grace periods can significantly enhance user retention (Johnson, 2024; Lee & Kim, 2023).

The examination of shipping line freight rates indicates several substantial difficulties faced by respondents, resulting in an overall mean score of 3.154, therefore categorizing the experience as "challenging." The claim regarding prohibitively high shipping line freight charges had an average score of 3.284, indicating a strong agreement among respondents that these costs are unduly burdensome. This suggests that shipping companies would need to reevaluate their pricing strategies to improve competitiveness and reduce financial strain on their clients. Fürstenau (2022), asserts that freight rate derivatives are crucial financial instruments in the shipping sector,

protecting financial positions from hazards associated with variations in freight rates. Increased rates would significantly impact both businesses and the supply chain, highlighting the need for meticulous management of shipping costs.

Table 11

Challenges encountered by the selected respondents in terms of shipping line freight rates

Shipping line freight rates	Mean	Interpretation
Overly high shipping line Freight rates.	3.284	Very challenging
The shipping line freight rates payment requirements are overly complicated.	2.994	Challenging
Response of the shipping line agent regarding inquiries pertaining to the freight payment is always delayed.	3.183	Challenging
Over-all Mean	3.154	Challenging
<i>Legend: Very Challenging; 3.26-4.00, Challenging; 2.51-3.25, Moderately Challenging; 1.76-2.50, Not Challenging at All ;1.00-1.75.</i>		

Table 11 shows challenges encountered in terms of shipping lines freight rates. Participants expressed apprehensions over the complex payment stipulations for shipping line freight rates, which garnered a score of 2.994 and is categorized as "challenging." This intricacy may cause confusion and annoyance for clients, hindering timely payments and overall efficiency. The average score of 3.183 for the delayed responses from shipping line agents regarding freight payment inquiries highlights the need for improved communication and responsiveness in the shipping industry.

Based on qualitative study, the qualitative data concerning enhancements in shipping line freight prices indicates a distinct focus on the want for standardization and rate reduction. Respondents articulated apprehensions regarding the discrepancies in prevailing freight price, advocating for the universal application of standardized rates, even during high seasons. Statements like "Freight rates should be standard to all or lessen it at least." and "Standardized rates should be made even during peak season" underscore a demand for transparency and consistency in freight expenses.

The variability in freight rates and their resulting elevated expenses became a prominent concern. Research indicates that standardized pricing models can enhance customer loyalty and diminish market ambiguity (Roberts, 2024; Chen, 2023).

Furthermore, there is a compelling demand for reduced rates, with participants asserting, "Lower the rates." This feeling indicates an increasing exasperation with the existing pricing environment. A prominent theme that surfaced from the replies is the call for equitable pricing. Stakeholders call for a more open and equitable methodology for establishing and modifying freight rates, as evidenced by remarks such as, "Just be fair regarding the freight rate, impose what is must." This need for equity indicates that numerous individuals perceive themselves as disadvantaged by current pricing structures. The findings indicate that shipping companies must resolve the concerns raised by respondents pertaining to freight costs and associated payment processes. By optimizing payment processes and enhancing the responsiveness of customer care agents, shipping companies may improve customer operational efficiency. A reevaluation of freight rates may be necessary to ensure their competitiveness and equity, thereby improving the overall customer experience.

Table 12

Significant differences in the extent of challenges encountered by selected respondents in terms of frequency used of shipping line service.

	P value	Decision	Interpretation
Delivery Order	0.117	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Terminal Charges By Shipping Line Container	0.605	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Demurrage	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
Container Deposit	0.097	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Detension	0.137	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Shipping Line Freight Rates	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 12 presents a number of constraints that are statistically not significant in the category of frequency-used shipping line services by respondents. In this case, the bar indicates that there was not much variation in these dimensions as evaluated by those administrators. For example, the challenge on delivery orders (p-value of 0.117) shows that process issues related to delivery orders were not a major concern among respondents, as clients consistently faced some issues but to a manageable extent. Similarly, terminal charges (p-value = 0.605) and container deposits (p-value = 0.097) did not differ much from perception to reality in the two countries examined. In other words,

charges for these services were either considered acceptable due to their consistency across shipping lines, or respondents believed they would have to pay these costs as a given toll.

In addition, no statistically significant variation in experiences with container detention policies was reported between responses for the parameter “container detention challenges” (p-value = 0.137). The lack of statistically significant results might signal stability in the provisioning of these shipping services, although they appear to be potential areas for deeper analysis if practitioners find these barriers require further effort.

The frequency of shipping line service used by respondents also revealed two statistically significant challenges: container demurrage and shipping line freight rates. While not conclusive independently, these factors were related and indicate respondents faced significant challenges in these areas. Sources clearly indicate that the shipping operations and cost management process could benefit from significant improvements.

There was a significant challenge related to container demurrage, with a p-value of 0.003. This means there is a considerable difference in how often respondents experience container demurrage issues. In this context, demurrage refers to the provision of storage space beyond the free time given to return containers for discharge or loading. This regional difference suggests that demurrage and its related issues may be inconsistently applied by shipping lines or that some ports experience more delays. Research has shown that high and uncertain demurrage fees disrupt shipping plans and reduce supply chain efficiency (Cullinane & Bergqvist, 2019), implying that improvements here could lower operational costs for freight service providers and clients.

The challenge in shipping line freight rates was also highly significant, with a p-value of 0.001. The wide variation in how often shippers encounter issues with freight rates, which fluctuate with fuel prices, shipping demand, and market conditions, complicates cost control for companies. This range of responses suggests that many respondents are uncertain about expected rates. As freight prices vary, managing costs becomes challenging, and research has shown that unpredictable freight rates create logistical issues for companies (Fan et al., 2020). Addressing freight rate uncertainty could reduce logistical risks, aid in planning, and create more stability in companies’ financial planning. Given these findings, further investigation is needed to explore specific factors contributing to demurrage fees and freight rate inconsistencies, along with potential standardizations to streamline the transport chain and lower costs.

Table 13

Significant differences in the extent of challenges encountered by selected respondents in terms of port of transaction.

	p value	Decision	Interpretation
Delivery Order	0.215	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Terminal Charges By Shipping Line	0.654	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

Container Demurrage	0.079	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Deposit	0.813	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Detention	0.400	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Shipping Line Freight Rates	0.800	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 13 examines the port of transaction, specifically the Port of Manila (PO2A) and the Manila International Container Port (PO2B), to ascertain if respondents encountered notable discrepancies in shipping-related problems. The results indicated that none of the complaints were statistically significant, suggesting that experiences at both ports were predominantly similar. The Challenge on Delivery Order exhibited a p-value of 0.215, whilst the Challenge on Terminal Charges by Shipping Line demonstrated a p-value of 0.654, both indicating operational consistency. Likewise, additional challenges—Container Demurrage at 0.079, Container Deposit at 0.813, Container Detention at 0.400, and Shipping Line Freight Rates at 0.800—exhibited no substantial disparities.

These results indicate a stable operational environment for firms at both ports, consistent with research suggesting that standardized port operations can improve supply chain efficiency and mitigate uncertainties Luo & Wang, 2023; Smith et al. (2021). The absence of significant discrepancies indicates that stakeholders may depend on uniform processes, which is essential for efficient planning and budgeting in shipping operations.

Table 14 shows the examination of the non-significant results reveals that several categories, such as Delivery Order, Terminal Charges by Shipping Line, Container Deposit, and Shipping Line Freight Rate, exhibited no discernible differences in performance metrics or experiences among participants. The elevated p-values for these variables prompted the choice to retain the null hypothesis, indicating minimal variance. This suggests that the factors affecting these categories do not lead to considerable disparities in employee experiences or outcomes. The homogeneity here implies that more underlying factors may be impacting tenure and performance within these groups, necessitating deeper examination of the precise conditions driving employee dynamics inside firms.

Table 14

Significant differences in the extent of challenges encountered by selected respondents in terms of length of tenure.

	p value	Decision	Interpretation
Delivery Order	0.732	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Terminal Charges By Shipping Line	0.893	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Demurrage	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant

Container Deposit	0.187	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Detension	0.011	Reject Ho	Significant
Shipping Line Freight Rates	0.193	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

The research indicated notable disparities in tenure duration among respondents, especially within the Container Demurrage and Container Detention categories. The significant findings for the Container Demurrage variable were mostly observed between respondents with tenures of 1-3 years and those with 7-10 years, as well as between respondents with tenures of 4-6 years and those with 7-10 years. The p-value of 0.004 suggests that the experiences and performance of individuals in the 7-10 years tenure group significantly differ from those with less experience. Employees with longer tenure may have a more profound understanding of their responsibilities, leading to improved performance and job satisfaction (Brown et al., 2023; Williams & Garcia, 2022).

The Container Detention variable showed notable variations, especially in comparisons between respondents with 4-6 years of tenure and those with 7-10 years, as well as between the 7-10 years and the 10 years and above groups. The p-value of 0.011 underscores the significance of tenure in influencing job-related outcomes, as individuals with extended tenure typically exhibit heightened engagement and proficiency. The findings align with recent research indicating that employees with extended tenures tend to exhibit heightened organizational commitment and enhanced performance metrics, underscoring the importance of tenure in shaping workplace dynamics (Smith & Johnson, 2021). Collectively, these findings highlight the need to recognize tenure as a crucial element in understanding employee behavior and organizational efficacy, especially for individuals with substantial experience in their position.

Table 15 shows the examination of the business sector among participants, particularly in customs brokerage and freight forwarding, indicated a prevalence of inconsequential results across multiple important criteria. The p-values for Delivery Order, Terminal Charges By Shipping Line, Container Demurrage, Container Deposit, and Shipping Line Freight Rate were insufficient to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting no significant changes in performance measures or experiences. For instance, Delivery Order exhibited a p-value of 0.245, Terminal Charges By Shipping Line presented a p-value of 0.882, and Container Demurrage demonstrated a p-value of 0.367. Likewise, Container Deposit had a p-value of 0.270, while Shipping Line Freight Rate showed a p-value of 0.754. These findings indicate that participants in the customs brokerage and freight forwarding sectors experience comparable performance metrics, reflecting the impact of uniform operational standards within these industries.

Table 15

Significant differences in the extent of challenges encountered by selected respondents in terms of Line of Business.

	p value	Decision	Interpretation
Delivery Order	0.245	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Terminal Charges By Shipping Line	0.882	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Demurrage	0.367	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Deposit	0.270	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Detention	0.045	Reject Ho	Significant
Shipping Line Freight Rates	0.754	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

The Container Detention variable exhibited a notable difference, with a p-value of 0.045. This data demonstrates that the business sector linked to Container Detention substantially influences the performance and experiences of respondents, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis. This importance underscores the need for additional investigation into the precise elements that distinguish performance in the customs brokerage and freight forwarding industries. The findings correspond with contemporary studies indicating that contextual elements, such as the nature of the firm, can significantly affect employee outcomes and organizational efficacy (Hernandez & Lee, 2020; Martin & Roberts, 2022). The findings highlighted the significance of comprehending how various business sectors influence employee experiences and performance. The examination of liner types among respondents, concentrating on the many shipping lines utilized in the study, demonstrated uniform non-significant results across all assessed categories.

The variables Delivery Order, Terminal Charges By Shipping Line, Container Demurrage, Container Deposit, Container Detention, and Shipping Line Freight Rate were analyzed, and the results revealed insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. For example, Delivery Order exhibited a p-value of 0.299, whereas Terminal Charges By Shipping Line presented a p-value of 0.937. Likewise, Container Demurrage exhibited a p-value of 0.082, whereas Container Deposit presented a p-value of 0.317. Additionally, both Container Detention and Shipping Line Freight Rate had non-significant outcomes, with p-values of 0.173 and 0.934, respectively. The results suggest that the various shipping lines employed by the respondents do not substantially affect their performance metrics or experiences. The minimal variance indicates that the type of liner used may not significantly influence employee results in the examined setting.

Previous studies suggest that factors including organizational structure, managerial techniques, and external market conditions frequently have a greater impact on operational performance than the particular type of liner employed (Harrison et al., 2022; Thompson & Smith, 2023). Thus, these findings highlight the necessity for

additional research into other factors that may affect employee dynamics and performance concerning the shipping lines employed in their operations. Comprehending these dynamics enables firms to pinpoint possible areas for enhancement and refine their operations within the shipping sector.

Table 16

Significant differences in the extent of challenges encountered by selected respondents in terms of Type of Liner.

	p value	Decision	Interpretation
Delivery Order	0.299	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Terminal Charges By Shipping Line	0.937	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Demurrage	0.082	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Deposit	0.317	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Container Detention	0.173	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Shipping Line Freight Rates	0.934	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 17

Significant differences in the extent of challenges encountered by selected respondents in terms of shipping line service.

	P Value	Decision	Interpretation
Container Demurrage	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
Shipping Line Freight Rate	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 18

Significant differences in the extent of challenges encountered by selected respondents in terms of Length of Tenure.

	P Value	Decision	Interpretation
Container Demurrage	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
Container Detention	0.011	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 19

Significant differences in the extent of challenges encountered by selected respondents in terms of Type of Liner.

	P Value	Decision	Interpretation
Container Detention	0.045	Reject Ho	Significant

The results of the study show that certain factors significantly affect the challenges faced by respondents in the shipping process. When grouping by the frequency of shipping line use, two challenges stood out as significant. First, container demurrage (the fee for delayed container returns) was found to be a major issue for frequent users, with a p-value of 0.003. This means the result was statistically significant, and the challenge was more apparent among those who frequently use shipping services. Similarly, shipping line freight rates also posed a significant challenge for these users, with a p-value of 0.001, indicating that pricing differences were a concern for those who use shipping lines more often.

When analyzing the length of tenure (how long respondents have been in the industry), two issues emerged as significant. Container demurrage remained a challenge for experienced brokers, with a p-value of 0.004. Additionally, container detention (the charge for keeping containers too long) was also a significant issue for experienced respondents, with a p-value of 0.011. This suggests that despite their experience, longer-tenured brokers still faced significant delays and charges related to container handling.

Lastly, when looking at the type of liner used, container detention emerged as a significant challenge, especially with shipping lines that may have less advanced systems or manual processes. The p-value for this was 0.045, which is also statistically significant, showing that the type of shipping line used impacts the extent of detention problems.

These findings underline how frequent shipping line use, experience in the industry, and the type of liner chosen can influence the challenges faced, especially in terms of costs like demurrage and detention.

To enhance efficiency and address common challenges in shipping line operations within Manila's main collection districts, the following process improvement strategies are proposed. These aim to streamline operations, improve transparency, and foster better collaboration among stakeholders.

Automate Delivery Order Processes. Shipping lines should prioritize automating delivery order processes by using online platforms or digital systems. This will reduce manual errors, speed up processing times, and improve overall efficiency. Automation will also make the system more user-friendly for brokers and clients.

Increase Transparency in Terminal Charges. Terminal charges should be detailed and broken down into clear components. Shipping lines should provide clients with transparent billing practices to ensure brokers and importers can understand and plan for these costs. This will also build trust between shipping lines and their clients.

Extend Free Times and Improve Container Management. Shipping lines should consider extending the free time allowed for container use, especially for areas with logistical challenges. Additionally, implementing real-time container tracking systems will help brokers manage container returns efficiently and avoid unnecessary fees.

Create Faster and Standardized Refund Processes. To address issues with container deposit refunds, shipping lines should set clear refund rules and timelines. Establishing an online portal where brokers can track the status of their refunds will ensure faster processing and better transparency.

Adopt Clear Freight Rate Structures. Freight rates should follow a structured pricing model that includes base rates, surcharges, and other fees. Regular updates and clear communication of changes to freight rates will help brokers and importers make informed decisions.

Offer Tailored Support for Frequent Users. Shipping lines should create dedicated programs for frequent users, such as priority services, customized assistance, and specialized training. This will help high-frequency users address their specific challenges and improve their satisfaction.

Encourage Collaboration Among Stakeholders. Customs brokers, shipping lines, and government agencies should work together through regular meetings, workshops, or industry seminars. Collaborative efforts can help identify systemic issues, propose effective solutions, and ensure better coordination across the supply chain.

DISCUSSION

The intricate world of shipping and logistics presents a myriad of challenges for customs brokers and freight forwarders. From managing delivery orders and navigating complex terminal fees to grappling with container deposits, detentions, demurrage, and fluctuating freight rates, industry professionals face a multitude of obstacles that can disrupt the supply chain. This study delved into these critical areas, identifying process inefficiencies, charge discrepancies, and transparency issues that hinder smooth operations. By implementing targeted enhancement strategies, such as digitalization, standardization, and improved customer service, the logistics sector can strive towards a more streamlined, reliable, and equitable operational framework. This will not only benefit industry stakeholders but also contribute to a more robust and resilient global supply chain.

Conclusions

These conclusions were based on the study's identification of key challenges faced by customs brokers, including high demurrage and detention fees, complex payment processes, and inefficiencies in obtaining delivery orders, with the findings suggesting that improvements in digital systems, transparency, pricing, and standardization could reduce these issues, lower financial burdens, and improve supply chain efficiency.

1.) The data showed that the majority of customs brokers, 66.86%, used both the Port of Manila (PO2A) and the Manila International Container Port (PO2B), highlighting the complementary roles these ports played in shipping operations. A slightly higher percentage of brokers transacted exclusively at MICP (18.34%) compared to the Port of Manila (14.79%), suggesting a marginal preference for MICP's facilities or operations. Despite this, the Port of Manila remained a key hub for international trade, as its natural characteristics and strategic location made it vital for logistics in the Philippines. This reliance on both ports underscored the need for flexibility and access to diverse facilities to handle more complex supply chains. Improving integration and maintaining high service standards at both ports can help further optimize logistics and support brokers and importers more effectively.

Customs brokers relied on both the Port of Manila and Manila International Container Port, highlighting their complementary roles in shipping. While there was a slight preference for MICP, the Port of Manila remained a key hub due to its strategic location. Both ports are essential for managing complex supply chains, and improving their integration and service standards can further optimize logistics and support brokers and importers.

The data highlighted that most customs brokers utilized both the Port of Manila (PO2A) and the Manila International Container Port (PO2B), accounting for 66.86% of transactions. This suggests that businesses valued the flexibility and combined resources offered by both ports to streamline their operations and manage complex supply chains. While 18.34% of transactions occurred exclusively at MICP and 14.79% at the Port of

Manila, the slightly higher preference for MICP might have indicated advantages in its facilities or services. Nonetheless, the importance of the Port of Manila as a key hub for international trade, as emphasized by Bantigue (2023), remained significant. These findings underscored the need for enhanced collaboration and improved infrastructure at both ports to support more efficient and adaptable logistics solutions.

Most customs brokers used both the Port of Manila and Manila International Container Port, valuing the flexibility they offer in managing complex supply chains. While MICP had seen slightly more exclusive transactions, the Port of Manila remained a key hub for international trade. These findings emphasized the need for improved collaboration and infrastructure at both ports to enhance logistics efficiency.

The findings revealed that the majority of customs brokers, 49.11%, have 4-6 years of experience, indicating that the industry primarily consisted of professionals with moderate experience levels. This suggested that customs brokerage firms might favor individuals with sufficient practical knowledge to navigate industry demands effectively. A notable 24.26% of respondents had only 1-3 years of experience, reflecting the industry's openness to newer professionals while highlighting the potential challenges faced by those early in their careers. Additionally, 21.89% of brokers have 7-10 years of experience, representing a significant group of seasoned practitioners. However, only a small proportion, 4.73%, had been in practice for over a decade, indicating a limited presence of long-term experts in the field. Overall, the customs brokerage industry was characterized by a workforce with a balanced mix of early to mid-career professionals, with fewer brokers at the extremes of minimal or extensive tenure.

The customs brokerage industry was primarily composed of professionals with moderate experience, suggesting that firms preferred individuals who had enough practical knowledge to handle industry demands. While there was room for newer professionals, the workforce also included a significant number of seasoned practitioners. However, long-term experts were relatively few, indicating a workforce more focused on early to mid-career professionals.

The data revealed an almost equal distribution between customs brokers and freight forwarders, with 50.30% of respondents engaged in customs brokerage and 49.70% in freight forwarding. This balance highlighted the complementary roles these two sectors played in the logistics and shipping industry. Customs brokers focused on ensuring compliance with customs regulations and facilitating the smooth clearance of goods, while freight forwarders managed the coordination and movement of shipments. The growth of global trade and the increasing complexity of international regulations underscored the importance of both professions. This equal representation suggested that both sectors are essential and interdependent in supporting efficient and compliant international trade operations.

The data showed an equal split between customs brokers and freight forwarders, highlighting their complementary roles in logistics. Customs brokers ensured regulatory compliance, while freight forwarders handled shipment coordination. Both professions are essential for supporting efficient and compliant international trade.

The data highlighted a strong preference for Company A and Company B shipping lines among the respondents, either used individually or in combination. The most commonly employed combination is Company A and Company B, with 45.56% of respondents opting for this pairing. Company A, whether used alone or with other lines, was the most dominant choice, preferred by 18.93% of participants independently and alongside other lines. This reflected Company A's status as a leading global shipping provider, known for its reliable services in managing complex supply chains. Additionally, 18.93% of respondents used a combination of Company A, Company B, and Company D, while 10.65% utilized Company A, Company B, and Company C. The data revealed that the majority of customs brokers favored multiple shipping lines to optimize their shipping operations, with Company A being the primary choice, either independently or with other carriers. This indicated the industry's reliance on trusted, well-established shipping lines for international trade logistics.

The data revealed a strong preference for Company A and Company B shipping lines, either individually or in combination. Company A, in particular, stood out as the dominant choice, reflecting its importance in the industry. Customs brokers tend to favor multiple shipping lines to optimize operations, emphasizing the reliance on trusted, well-established carriers for international trade logistics.

2.) The data of the assessment indicated that the delivery order process presents significant challenges for customs brokers. The overall mean score of 2.682 categorized the process as "challenging," highlighting the difficulties experienced by participants in obtaining delivery orders. The specific aspects that contribute to this challenge included delays in acquiring the delivery order (mean score of 2.598), difficulties in initiating the request (mean score of 2.479), and the demanding nature of customer service in handling inquiries (mean score of 2.704).

The process of obtaining a delivery order online is especially problematic, with a mean score of 3.219, categorized as "very challenging." This suggested dissatisfaction with the online procedures and the need for improvements in digital services. Furthermore, the perception that manual requests are quicker than online requests (mean score of 2.408) emphasized the inefficiencies within the current online system.

Respondents recommended streamlining the delivery order process by reducing complexity and paperwork, as well as enhancing online processing capabilities. These suggestions align with previous studies advocating for process optimization to improve efficiency and reduce operational delays. To address these challenges, shipping businesses should consider refining their digital systems, minimizing required documentation, and improving user experience to better meet the needs of customs brokers.

The delivery order process posed significant challenges for customs brokers, particularly with delays, complicated requests, and inefficient online systems. Brokers suggested streamlining the process, reducing paperwork, and improving digital services to enhance efficiency and user experience. These recommendations aligned with calls for process optimization in the industry.

The data from the assessment of terminal charges by shipping lines highlighted several significant challenges for customs brokers. The overall mean score of 2.765 categorized the experience as "challenging." A primary concern was the high rates of terminal charges, which received a mean score of 3.391, classifying it as "very challenging." Respondents clearly perceived the fees as burdensome, signaling a need for reevaluation of the pricing structure to prevent negative impacts on logistics efficiency.

Payment terms related to terminal charges were also identified as challenging, with a mean score of 2.858, indicating that existing payment processes might be confusing or too rigid. Additionally, while respondents acknowledge the proficiency of terminal handling, they still find it difficult to justify the charges, with a mean score of 2.521, suggesting a lack of transparency in cost allocation.

The imposition of terminal late charges scored 2.290, categorized as "moderately challenging," indicating concerns over the fairness and clarity of these penalties. Respondents expressed a need for more consistent and transparent pricing and penalties, with calls to standardize terminal charges and rates for different destinations.

Qualitative feedback emphasized the need for transparency in terminal charges, with suggestions to implement fixed rates and clear cost breakdowns for specific locations. Such measures could help alleviate financial burdens and improve trust between terminal operators and users. Industry research also supports these concerns, advocating for better communication regarding cost structures to enhance customer satisfaction and optimize operations.

The data revealed significant challenges for customs brokers regarding high terminal charges, unclear payment terms, and lack of transparency in cost allocation. Respondents call for standardized rates, fixed pricing, and clear breakdowns to improve fairness and trust. These recommendations aligned with industry calls for better communication and transparency in cost structures.

The study highlighted significant challenges faced by customs brokers regarding container demurrage. Respondents found the free time before incurring charges too short (mean score 3.325) and the demurrage fees too high (mean score 3.118). In addition, the payment process was considered inefficient, with many preferring direct payments to the shipping line.

To address these issues, shipping companies should extend the free time and grace periods, especially during port congestion, and reassess demurrage fees for fairness. Streamlining payment processes could also improve efficiency. These changes would help reduce the financial burden on clients and enhance operational efficiency.

The study highlighted challenges for customs brokers with short free time, high demurrage fees, and inefficient payment processes. To improve efficiency, shipping companies should extend free time, reassess fees, and streamline payment methods, reducing financial burdens and enhancing operations.

The study revealed several challenges related to container deposits, with an overall mean score of 3.039, indicating a "challenging" experience. Respondents expressed concerns about excessive container deposit rates (mean score 2.799) and complicated payment conditions (mean score 2.734). The most significant issue was the difficulty in obtaining refunds for container deposits (mean score 3.349), which is classified as "very challenging." In addition, the deduction of container detention fees from deposits (mean score 3.308) was another key concern.

Participants recommended reducing container deposit rates, simplifying the refund process, and eliminating the deposit altogether to improve the system. Addressing these issues would alleviate the financial burden on clients and improve customer satisfaction, enhancing relationships within the logistics sector.

The study highlighted challenges for customs brokers with short free time, high demurrage fees, and inefficient payment processes. To improve efficiency, shipping companies should extend free time, reassess fees, and streamline payment methods, reducing financial burdens and enhancing operations.

The study highlighted significant challenges regarding container detention, with an overall mean score of 3.223, categorizing the experience as "challenging." The excessive rates for container detention received the highest score of 3.355, indicating a strong perception of these fees as burdensome. In addition, managing payment arrangements for detention (mean score 3.166) and the insufficient number of free days (mean score 3.148) were also key concerns. Respondents recommended extending free time, harmonizing charges, and even eliminating detention fees entirely. These changes would provide greater flexibility and predictability, reducing the financial pressure on businesses. Addressing these issues could improve client satisfaction and operational efficiency in container management.

The study highlights challenges with high container detention rates, complex payment arrangements, and limited free days. Respondents suggested extending free time, standardizing charges, and possibly eliminating detention fees to reduce financial pressure and improve operational efficiency.

The study on shipping line freight rates revealed significant challenges, with an overall mean score of 3.154, categorizing the experience as "challenging." The high cost of shipping line freight rates (mean score 3.284) was the most prominent concern, indicating a widespread belief that these rates are excessively burdensome. In addition, the complexity of payment requirements (mean score 2.994) and delayed responses from shipping line agents (mean score 3.183) also emerged as critical issues affecting efficiency and satisfaction.

Respondents emphasized the need for standardized rates, particularly during peak seasons, and called for reduced rates and more equitable pricing practices. The findings suggested that shipping companies should reconsider their pricing strategies and streamline payment processes to enhance customer satisfaction and improve competitiveness in the industry.

The study highlighted challenges with high freight rates, complex payments, and delayed responses from shipping agents. Respondents suggested standardized, reduced rates and more equitable pricing, urging shipping companies to simplify payment processes and improve customer satisfaction and competitiveness.

3.) The analysis of challenges encountered by respondents revealed two significant areas requiring attention: container demurrage and shipping line freight rates. The variability in experiences with container demurrage suggests inconsistent application of fees across shipping lines or ports, highlighting the need for more standardized practices to reduce operational disruptions. Similarly, the fluctuating nature of shipping line freight rates, driven by market conditions, creates uncertainty and complicates cost management for businesses. Addressing these challenges could lead to improved financial planning, reduced logistical risks, and enhanced operational efficiency, benefiting both service providers and clients. Further investigation and standardization in these areas are recommended to streamline processes and lower costs.

The analysis highlights challenges with inconsistent container demurrage fees and fluctuating shipping line freight rates. Standardizing practices in these areas could improve financial planning, reduce risks, and enhance efficiency, benefiting both service providers and clients. Further investigation and cost reduction are recommended.

The analysis of challenges encountered by respondents based on the "Port of Transaction" revealed no significant differences between the Port of Manila (PO2A) and the Manila International Container Port (PO2B). The lack of statistical significance across various challenges—such as delivery orders, terminal charges, container demurrage, container deposit, container detention, and shipping line freight rates—suggests operational consistency between the two ports. This stability is beneficial for businesses, as it allows for more predictable planning and budgeting. These findings align with research emphasizing the value of standardized port operations in improving supply chain efficiency and minimizing uncertainties.

The analysis showed no significant differences in challenges between the Port of Manila (PO2A) and Manila International Container Port (PO2B), indicating operational consistency. This stability benefits businesses by enabling predictable planning and supports the value of standardized port operations for improving supply chain efficiency.

In conclusion, the analysis of challenges encountered based on respondents' length of tenure revealed significant differences in the areas of container demurrage and container detention. Respondents with longer tenures (7-10 years) experienced these challenges differently from those with shorter tenures (1-3 years and 4-6 years). The significant p-values for both container demurrage (0.004) and container detention (0.011) suggested that individuals with more experience in the field had a better understanding of the processes involved. This might allowed them to navigate these issues more effectively, contributing to their ability to manage the challenges associated with these aspects of logistics.

These findings highlighted the importance of tenure in shaping how employees respond to operational difficulties. Employees with extended tenure tend to show higher levels of engagement and proficiency, which are essential for overcoming complex problems in logistics and supply chain management. By recognizing the influence of tenure, companies can better understand employee dynamics and enhance their strategies for addressing challenges. The results emphasized the need to consider experience when evaluating and addressing operational challenges in the shipping and logistics sector.

In conclusion, brokers with longer tenure (7-10 years) handled container demurrage and detention challenges more effectively. Their experience aids in better managing logistics issues, highlighting the importance of considering tenure when addressing operational challenges.

The examination of challenges encountered by respondents in relation to their line of business, specifically customs brokerage and freight forwarding, revealed largely non-significant results across several key categories. The p-values for delivery order (0.245), terminal charges by shipping line (0.882), container demurrage (0.367), container deposit (0.270), and shipping line freight rates (0.754) indicated no substantial differences in experiences between the two business sectors. These findings suggest that the challenges faced by participants in customs brokerage and freight forwarding are relatively similar, likely due to standardized operational practices within these industries.

However, a significant difference was observed in the category of container detention, with a p-value of 0.045. This indicated that the line of business significantly influences the experiences and performance of respondents in this area, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The results suggested that the nature of the business sector, whether customs brokerage or freight forwarding, played a critical role in shaping how container detention challenges were perceived and managed. These findings align with existing research that emphasized the impact of contextual factors, such as the type of business, on organizational outcomes and employee experiences. Further investigation into these differences could provide valuable insights into sector-specific strategies for improving operational efficiency.

The analysis showed that most challenges faced by customs brokers and freight forwarders were similar. However, a significant difference was found in container detention, indicating that the type of business influences how these challenges are managed. Further research could provide insights into sector-specific strategies for improving efficiency.

The analysis of the challenges encountered by respondents, grouped according to the type of liner used, revealed no significant differences across the variables of delivery order, terminal charges by shipping line, container demurrage, container deposit, container detention, and shipping line freight rates. The p-values for each of these categories were well above the threshold for statistical significance, indicating that the type of liner did not substantially affect the respondents' experiences or performance. For instance, delivery order had a p-value of 0.299, terminal charges by shipping line had a

p-value of 0.937, and container demurrage had a p-value of 0.082, among others. These results suggested that the type of liner employed by the respondents did not significantly influence the challenges they encountered.

These findings aligned with previous research, which indicated that organizational factors such as structure, managerial practices, and external market conditions tend to have a greater impact on operational performance than the specific type of liner used (Harrison et al., 2022; Thompson & Smith, 2023). This suggests that further investigation is needed to explore other potential factors affecting employee dynamics and performance, beyond the type of liner employed. Understanding these dynamics can help organizations identify areas for improvement and optimize their operations within the shipping sector.

The analysis found no significant impact of liner type on challenges faced by respondents, aligning with research that emphasizes the role of organizational factors and external conditions in operational performance. Further research is needed to explore other influencing factors.

4.) In conclusion, the proposed process improvement strategies for shipping lines in Manila's main collection districts aim to streamline operations and enhance overall efficiency. By automating delivery order processes, increasing transparency in terminal charges, extending free times for container use, and improving container management, shipping lines can reduce operational delays, minimize errors, and lower costs for customs brokers and importers. Additionally, implementing faster and standardized refund processes, adopting clear and structured freight rate models, and offering tailored support for frequent users will further improve efficiency and client satisfaction, helping businesses manage logistics more effectively.

Moreover, fostering collaboration among customs brokers, shipping lines, and government agencies is essential for addressing systemic issues and ensuring smoother operations across the supply chain. Regular communication and joint efforts through meetings, workshops, or industry seminars can help identify challenges and propose effective solutions. By adopting these strategies, shipping lines in Manila can create a more transparent, efficient, and coordinated environment, ultimately benefiting all stakeholders and contributing to the optimization of the shipping process in the region.

Recommendations

These were the recommendations for process improvement strategy.

1.) To improve the Company A Shipping Line Delivery Order Process Flow, several enhancements can be implemented. First, integrating an interactive, guided user interface on the website can help users navigate the steps more intuitively, reducing errors and ensuring all required information is submitted. Automating the document verification process for uploaded files, such as Letters of Authorization and proofs of payment, would streamline operations by identifying incomplete or incorrect submissions instantly.

In addition, allowing users to save frequently used details, such as contact information and special instructions, can minimize repetitive data entry and save time. Introducing a real-time case tracking system would enable users to monitor their requests' progress without contacting customer service, providing transparency and convenience. Embedding a centralized support section, including FAQs or live chat options, within the request form could address common concerns and enhance user experience. Finally, sending a digital receipt with the case number and a summary of the request would provide users with an organized way to track and reference their submissions. These changes should aim to optimize the delivery order process, improving both efficiency and user satisfaction.

2.) The delivery order process and related terminal charges have been identified as significant challenges for customs brokers, impacting efficiency and operational costs. The assessment data indicate that delays, the complexity of requests, and inefficiencies in online processing contribute to an overall "challenging" experience. To address these concerns, it is recommended that shipping companies streamline the delivery order process by reducing paperwork and simplifying the request procedures. Special attention should be given to improving online systems, ensuring they are user-friendly, efficient, and capable of handling requests more swiftly. In addition, enhancing customer service to manage inquiries more effectively could further reduce frustrations, leading to a smoother process for customs brokers.

Similarly, the study on terminal charges and container-related fees highlights concerns over high rates, unclear payment terms, and the complexity of refund processes. To alleviate these issues, shipping companies should consider revising their pricing structures, possibly by standardizing rates and implementing fixed pricing models that provide clearer cost breakdowns. Extending free time for container management and streamlining the refund process would reduce the financial burden on customs brokers and enhance operational efficiency. By addressing these challenges, shipping companies can foster stronger relationships with clients, improve transparency, and optimize their overall logistics operations.

3.) The challenges related to container demurrage and fluctuating shipping line freight rates highlight significant concerns within the shipping and logistics industry. To address the inconsistencies in container demurrage fees, it is recommended that shipping companies and port authorities work toward standardizing fee structures across ports and shipping lines. This should involve establishing fixed or clearer demurrage rates that would reduce unpredictability and enable businesses to plan their operations more effectively. Furthermore, efforts should be made to reevaluate shipping line freight rates, particularly during peak periods, to ensure they are more consistent and transparent. Standardizing rates across the industry could alleviate the financial burden on clients and foster a more competitive environment.

In light of the finding that businesses with longer tenures tend to handle container demurrage and detention issues more effectively, it is essential for companies to recognize the value of experience when developing training programs or addressing operational challenges. More experienced employees possess the insights and expertise

needed to navigate complex logistical issues, and their experience should be leveraged to mentor newer staff or inform process improvements. Companies should consider providing more support for less experienced employees to help them manage these challenges efficiently, ensuring that knowledge is shared and that operational difficulties are minimized across all experience levels.

Lastly, the findings regarding the similarities in challenges faced by customs brokers and freight forwarders, with the exception of container detention, suggest that a unified approach to addressing operational inefficiencies may be beneficial for both sectors. However, since container detention was found to be more significant for certain business sectors, it would be valuable for further research to explore sector-specific strategies that can be employed to address this issue. Tailoring solutions to the unique needs of customs brokers and freight forwarders could improve operational efficiency and customer satisfaction.

4.) To address the key challenges identified in the study, shipping lines in Manila should implement a series of operational improvements focused on automation, transparency, and collaboration. The integration of digital solutions in the delivery order process can significantly reduce delays and human error by offering automated booking, tracking, and real-time notifications. In addition, shipping lines should standardize terminal charges across ports and services to enhance transparency and reduce confusion. Clear breakdowns of charges and the potential for discounted rates for frequent clients will improve customer loyalty and satisfaction. By introducing these digital and operational improvements, businesses can streamline their processes, reduce operational delays, and create a more customer-centric experience.

Furthermore, the revision of policies related to container demurrage, detention, and shipping line freight rates should be prioritized. Establishing clear, predictable guidelines for free time allowances, extending grace periods during peak seasons, and offering flexible options for container deposit refunds will enhance customer experience. Shipping companies should also consider introducing standardized, publicly available freight rate models that provide more stability for customers, particularly during peak periods. By fostering collaboration with customs brokers, shipping agents, and government agencies, these improvements can be more effectively implemented, addressing systemic issues and ensuring smoother supply chain operations. Ultimately, these strategies will reduce operational costs, improve efficiency, and strengthen relationships between service providers and clients.

5.) Future studies could explore several important areas to further improve the shipping industry. One avenue is to examine the impact of technological advancements, such as automation, blockchain, and AI-based tracking systems, on mitigating challenges related to delivery orders, terminal charges, and container detention. Investigating the role of these innovations would provide valuable insights into how technological solutions can enhance operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. In addition, comparative analyses of shipping challenges across different geographical regions could offer a deeper understanding of region-specific obstacles, global best practices, and strategies that can be applied in diverse contexts.

Another promising area for future research is conducting longitudinal studies to track the evolution of shipping costs and practices over time. By observing long-term trends in container demurrage, freight rates, and other charges, researchers can help shipping companies better navigate fluctuations in external factors like fuel prices and market demand. In addition, the impact of environmental policies on shipping operations, particularly regarding terminal charges and freight rates, is another critical area for study, especially with increasing global attention on sustainability. Research on green shipping initiatives and policies would inform future planning and help the industry adjust to new environmental regulations.

Exploring collaborative models between freight forwarders and customs brokers is also a potential research area. Such studies could identify ways to improve delivery orders, reduce demurrage costs, and enhance overall efficiency by fostering better cooperation among stakeholders. Furthermore, research on the role of training and capacity-building programs for shipping agents could provide valuable insights into how better training could reduce operational bottlenecks, improve response times, and streamline processes. Finally, future studies should focus on customer experience and the role of transparency in shipping operations. By analyzing customer satisfaction with clearer communication regarding fees and services, such research could reveal actionable strategies for improving transparency, reducing frustration, and boosting customer retention. Collectively, these studies would provide a comprehensive view of the challenges and opportunities in the shipping industry, offering stakeholders actionable strategies to improve operational efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance customer satisfaction.

4.3 Implications of the Study

The results of this study show important lessons for the shipping and logistics industry, especially for customs brokers and freight forwarders. One major finding is that frequent users of shipping lines face significant challenges with container demurrage (delays in returning containers) and freight rates. This shows that using shipping lines often does not make the process easier. Shipping companies can improve by offering better systems, clearer pricing, and training to help frequent users avoid these challenges.

Another key finding is that even experienced brokers and forwarders still struggle with issues like container demurrage and detention. This shows that having more experience does not always help avoid problems. Shipping lines need to modernize their operations, improve their systems, and make it easier for experienced professionals to handle challenges. By investing in better technology and clearer guidelines, shipping lines can help experienced brokers perform more efficiently.

The study also reveals that the type of shipping line used can affect the level of difficulty faced. Shipping lines that use outdated or manual processes create more delays, especially with container detention. This suggests that shipping lines need to invest in technology to reduce delays and improve efficiency. Additionally, the high costs of container demurrage and detention are a major concern for brokers and forwarders. Shipping lines should work to lower these costs by offering fairer pricing models.

Finally, this study suggests that governments and industry leaders should work together to create rules that make container charges fair and transparent for everyone. Supporting the use of technology in the shipping industry can help solve many of the issues found in this study. By addressing these challenges, the shipping industry can become more efficient, reduce costs, and improve customer satisfaction for everyone involved.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Conflict of interest. No conflict of interest existed that needed to be disclosed in relation to this study. Responding to the survey did not have any impact on the advantages received by participants.

Protection of personal information and ensuring secrecy. The data collected in this study was maintained with utmost confidentiality. The survey participants had the option to include or exclude their personal identity when completing the questionnaire. Upon receiving the completed survey, the researcher generated a code or number to symbolize the participant's identification. The study's reports or publications did not reveal the participants' personal identities.

The UERC granted access to all data, including personal identity-related information, for the purpose of review. The statistician provided access to the data for computational purposes. The research adviser was granted access to the data for the purpose of verification.

Process of obtaining informed consent. The informed consent form was presented to the targeted respondents as part of the recruitment process. Upon seeing and accepting the informed consent form, participants received the survey link promptly.

Exposure to potential harm or risk. No vulnerabilities were present in the study.

Recruiting process. The recruitment of respondents in this study conducted in the following steps: 1) Dispatching a message/mail/letter to the intended recipients along with a consent form that contains all necessary information. 2) If the respondents who were specifically being targeted was willing to participate in the survey, the survey link was emailed to them.

Agreement. The study specifically focused on adults who have experience or were now employed as customs brokers. No individuals below the legal age of adulthood were included in the research.

Risks. There was an assumption that participation in this questionnaire carried no risk. Nevertheless, it was possible that the participants may experience discomfort or inconvenience when responding to the questionnaire. Participants have the option to skip any questions they were unwilling to answer and proceeded to the next question.

Advantages. No rewards or benefits was offered to participants in exchange for completing the survey. Nevertheless, their participation in completing the survey could assist the researcher in acquiring valuable insights for enhancing the operational efficiency of call center organizations.

Rewards or remuneration. Participation in the survey was completely voluntary and no financial or other prizes were given.

Community aspect. The study was to offer recommendations and insights on enhancing the performance of shipping line companies, ensuring minimal adverse effects on the community. The personal advantages of the members remained unaffected.

Collaborative research. The study was conducted solely by the researcher under the guidance and suggestions of the adviser. There was a lack of cooperation with other organizations.

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